

Optimizing field technician collaboration through implementing digital twin technology in IT service management

This paper is Systematic Literature Review using Barbara Kitchenham methods.

We provided **.ris** file after conducted 3 stage of Barbara Kitchenham methods on attached

Barbara Kitchenham is a renowned researcher known for her contributions to evidence-based software engineering, particularly in the area of systematic literature reviews and empirical software engineering. A literature review conducted using Barbara Kitchenham's approach would typically follow a structured and rigorous methodology to systematically and unbiasedly synthesize existing research findings [13]. This paper utilizes a methodological framework based on Barbara Kitchenham's research. This framework enables a systematic approach to selecting articles and conducting thorough content evaluation. The focus is on integrating automotive and field service technician management with the digital twin approach. Here's how a literature review using Kitchenham's approach might be conducted will be explained below.

Fig. 1. Kitchenham flow process

B. Research Question Formulation

Define clear research questions or objectives that guide the literature review. These questions should be specific, focused, and relevant to the topic of interest. For example, in the context of optimizing field technician collaboration using Digital Twin technology in the automotive industry, research questions could include:

- What are the potential benefits of implementing Digital Twin technology in the automotive field of service management?
- How can Digital Twin technology be effectively integrated into automotive field service management to enhance real-time communication and collaboration among field technicians?
- What are automotive companies' key challenges in adopting and implementing Digital Twin solutions to optimize field technician collaboration?

C. Search Strategy Development

Design a comprehensive search strategy to identify relevant literature sources. This may involve searching electronic databases (e.g., IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, Scopus) using a combination of keywords related to the research topic (e.g., "Digital Twin," "field service management," "automotive industry," "collaboration," "IoT," "AI"). Kitchenham's approach emphasizes transparency and reproducibility in search methodology.

TABLE I. SEARCH STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT

Search Strategy	Description
Type of Publication	Articles published in conferences and academic reputation journals

Language	English-language publications
Year	2018-2024
Search Field	Title, abstracts, and keywords
Search keyword	("digital twin" AND optimising or combine with digital twin AND collaboration OR implementing OR field service AND type of field technician OR framework OR enhance AND virtual OR potential AND challenge OR issue).

D. Study Selection

The researchers used Mendeley, a software for managing references, to facilitate the selection of journals. The software may be found at www.mendeley.com. The primary articles were selected from established journals specifically addressing the asset and resource aspects associated [13] with digital twin technologies. The process involved evaluating titles and abstracts to eliminate specific primary research, followed by a subsequent round of exclusion based on a thorough review of the complete texts to finalize the chosen studies.

E. Data Extraction and Synthesis:

Gather information from specific studies, such as key results and methods of research and ultimately the final draft. Kitchenham's approach emphasizes the importance of data extraction templates or forms to facilitate consistent and structured data collection. Data synthesis involves organizing and summarizing examined the data to identify repeating topics, trends and issues within the research.

From the selected research, a total of 30 papers have been specifically picked for inclusion in each round. These papers will be deeper analysis and meticulously studied in further detail.

TABLE II. DATA EXTRACTION

Source	Studies Found	Candidate studies	Selected studies
Scopus	25	15	8
IEEE Xplore	38	25	2
ScienceDirect	17	10	3
Scholar	90	38	15
Springer Link	30	12	2
Total	200	110	30

F. Analysis and Reporting

Analyze synthesized findings to address the research questions and objectives of the literature review. Kitchenham's approach advocates for transparent reporting of the review process, including detailed descriptions of search strategies, criteria for selecting studies, methods of data extraction, and techniques for synthesis. The literature review report should present a clear narrative that integrates findings from diverse sources and provides insights into current knowledge on the research topic.

I. RESULT AND FINDING

From the extraction that has been selected, the author gathers and finds the most fulfilled value to related research. Based on what has been found, based on the table ahead, are the year and quantity of research that match.

Fig. 2. Selected Studies

All references indeed need to have relation and relevant research; therefore author seeks an active keyword to describe and explain all studies that have been found as referred to in the table below.

TABLE III. ACTIVE KEYWORDS DT IN FIELD TECH IN ITSM

Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Digital twin Machine Learning Manufacturing Automotive Industry Field Technician Decision Interaction Effectiveness	Control Manufacturing Industry Limitation Communication DT Technology Digital Twins Lifecycle Efficiency	CPS Performance Virtual model AI Predictive Maintenance Big Data Optimization Real Time Efficiency

Fig. 3. Keywords co-occurrence VosViewer